

MECHANISMS OF FORMATION OF SOCIALLY ACTIVE CIVIC COMPETENCES OF STUDENTS IN THE CONTENT OF ACADEMIC SUBJECTS IN PRIMARY GRADES

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ANNOTATION

Prospective history teachers face the challenge of navigating stereotypes that have limited the subject to rigid and memorization-based learning methods, presenting it as a closed-off realm of knowledge lacking meaning and interest for many students. Studies examining social science teaching consistently underscore the significant educational value that history holds. Whether through inquiry-based or discovery-focused classroom activities, history engages students in primary cognitive skills like classification, analysis, reflection, and inference.

Key words: social science teaching, discovery-focused, classroom activity, initial training, school history, reliability;

Rather than conceiving school history as a fixed body of knowledge, it should be viewed as an ongoing construction of knowledge. Recommendations arising from research suggest a shift towards a subject that encourages students to question the present and the past, draw causal relationships, challenge prevailing explanations, propose hypotheses, identify biases, craft rational and informed explanations of historical events, and draw lessons from historical contexts, among other approaches.

First: the running of four initial training sessions for observers on the observation modality, selection and access to the scenarios. The main interest was to ensure agreement between observers for greater objectivity and precision of the records obtained, as well as to meet the minimum requirements of reliability (objectivity) in the study.

Second: the definitive design of the observation guide and the field notes recording template with the general questions and dimensions to guide the collection of information related to the objectives and theoretical framework of the study. The fieldwork was carried out through a non-participant, direct and open observation modality, with an average duration of one hour per session. Descriptive-narrative records (field notes and memoranda) were chosen, often supplemented with the use of auxiliary means to obtain audio recordings and photographs, with the prior informed consent of the students' legal guardians. Ethical issues and questions regarding the protection of personal data in these situations were approved by the Ethics Committee of the University of Barcelona.

The observational record advanced via selective logic (Spradley, 1980) in each session, initially descriptive and gradually more focused as the activity progressed to focus on its more specific dimensions regarding the educational value of resources and the pupils' competence development: the contents dealt with, the development of social competences (through the narrative and argumentative competence expressed in school narratives and speeches), the attitudes of pupils, the experiences and experiences in the classroom, the role of the teacher and the material and socio-affective conditions of the climate in the contexts studied. The records were transcribed to ensure the confidentiality and anonymity of the participants.

Third: the development of group work sessions parallel to the observations in order to share impressions, coordinate classification of the data and discuss characteristics of the observation, saturation of information and categories of emerging analysis. Data analysis began at the moment of data collection and consisted of a continuous review of the material obtained, to redirect and guide the information collected in the same observational process of each context, considering the most relevant content categories that were emerging. Both teaching units allowed for the creation of a critical and inclusive learning environment in the classroom, promoting attitudes in keeping with responsible democratic citizenship. Let us now turn our attention to some interesting nuances that have been identified for online competence development with regard to active citizenship and critical citizenship.

If we focus more specifically on the evidence linked to the development of active citizenship, during the implementation of the teaching units there are references to promoting the responsibility of adolescents towards social issues, especially to participatory and ethical values in the face of issues of a political nature and civic engagement. Both teaching units promote attitudes typical of responsible citizenship, but in line with the previous results, “Athens” clearly enhances their development, as illustrated by the following fragments of the records obtained:

So that they understand the ecclesia refers to the school board and they do consider it more democratic if all the representatives that make up the school community— parents, students, teachers, management teams, cleaning staff, janitors, etc. can participate, and what it would be like if only teachers sat on the school board.

The proposed teaching materials enhance the analysis of social reality and the construction of structured historical knowledge, based on work on citizen social participation in Athenian democracy, covered in the Athens teaching unit.

On more detailed investigation into the work carried out from both teaching units for the exercise of critical citizenship, the analysis of observational records reveals two key aspects: the value given to the treatment of conflictive issues from a historical and critical analysis of social reality to advance the attitudes and skills underlying this competence in the classroom: The students criticized the eugenicist view, considering it clearly racist (...). Some of them argue that this theory is deeply unfair and they totally disagree. They say that the education one receives can change this.

As we have seen, the students analyzed were presented with materials based on the initial problem statement and hypothesis; the analysis of historical sources of different natures in which opposing points of view were put forward; and in the interpretation of events avoiding a presentist outlook. The teacher’s role was crucial in imbuing the classroom with a suitable climate for this purpose, promoting debates, trying to lay the foundations for discussion among students and establishing agreements among them. At the same time, the teacher tried to create participatory classroom environments, where all reasoned and structured points of view of members had their place.

These spaces generated discussion and exchange of experiences and daily experiences that have allowed us to create active and motivating conceptions of the learning context designed. In this way, it has been possible to verify in the sample analyzed that the students showed motivation and interest, fundamental aspects for the improvement and achievement of the learning objectives.

Conclusions .The interpretation of results leads us to pose an important challenge for the study of social sciences teaching methodology, for citizenship education and for schools. As has been shown, teachers form an essential part both for choosing the most appropriate content and methodologies, and for generating learning environments that foster the development of active and critical citizenship. Therefore, it is essential that teacher training should adapt to these needs. We recommend a review of the Master's in Teacher Training syllabus for future teachers of secondary education, and at the same time, insist on the importance of the Humanities in our society.

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